

Training Needs Assessment and Employee Performance at County Governments of Nakuru

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15383795>

Published Date: 11-May-2025

Abstract: The purpose of the study was to establish the effect of training needs assessment on performance of employees at the county government of Nakuru, Kenya. The study anchors on the human capital theory. This study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population was all the employees at supervisory level, Middle Managers of Nakuru County. The study adopted census since the target population is small. Data collection instrument was structured questionnaire. Pilot testing was done to test the validity and reliability of research instrument. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics and presented in tabular form through the use of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 27. Data was subjected to correlation and Multiple Regression Statistical Methods to test the significant levels of the independent over the dependent variables. Based on the findings, the study concluded that training needs assessment had a significant effect on performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya. The study came up with the following recommendations; the management should come up with HRD policy and other HRM&D guidelines in the counties, planning for training shall be guided by the outcome of Training Needs Assessment and shall be designed in line with identified performance gaps linking training to closing of such gaps. The study findings was to be useful for human resource management practice, policy formulation and research works. The study findings will also to help counties in evaluating the importance of training and development on employee performance at County governments in Kenya. The findings will provide insights into the effectiveness of current training initiatives and inform policy decisions on capacity-building strategies to enhance public sector performance at the county level.

Keywords: Training Needs Assessment, Employee Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced business environment, the importance of corporate training in enhancing employee performance and productivity cannot be overstated. It's a strategic investment that equips employees with the necessary skills to excel in their current roles and prepares them for the evolving demands of the future workplace. This continuous learning and development process ensures the company's growth, competitiveness, and innovation (Pete Ford 2025). While there are multiple forms of corporate training, instructor-led training (ILT) has shown particular effectiveness. As a traditional and interactive form of training, it allows for real-time feedback, in-depth discussions, and tailored instruction, facilitating a comprehensive learning experience (Pete Ford 2025). Increased instances of globalization and the search for high returns and competitiveness, has pushed organizations to seek a means of attracting, retaining skilled, committed and motivated workforce (F. Baldi, L. Trigeorgis 2020). In essence, due to the changing workloads, market needs, operational work adjustments and changing work tasks, creating a need to keep employees updated from time to time on the current happenings and changes at the workplace.

Training is the most basic function of human resources management. It is the systematic application of formal processes to help people to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for them to perform their jobs satisfactorily (Armstrong, 2020). These activities have become widespread human resource management practices in organizations worldwide (Hughes et al., 2019). In today's business world, training is the main strategy to perform the institutional objectives. It helps to improve employee and employer performance (R. A. G. Khan et al., 2011; Ruttledge & Cathcart, 2019). Employees are the most precious asset for any organization in building up or destroying its reputation and profitability (Elnaga & Imran, 2013). Some of the factors that determine the performance of employees are training of employees, organizational policies, working situations, job satisfaction, interactions with in the organization (Cascio & Montealegre, 2023). Thus, training is one of the most effective tools to enhance the employee performance and to achieve the organizational objectives and goals effectively and efficiently (Afroz, Citation 2018; Garavan et al., 2020).

According to Larsen (2017) organizations seeking chances of improving their workforce performance and productivity must then invest in training and re-training their employees. This means that well trained and equipped employees are able to push for the organizational agenda and meet the set strategic goals. Training is seen as a valuable tool and an investment in the organization that helps to improve profitability, reduce operational costs and increase employee motivation, commitment and effectiveness.

Training is very crucial in organizations because new employees are continuously recruited to fill positions left vacant or the newly created positions and they must therefore be trained to work in the specific organizational context. As such training and development activities increase the productivity at an individual level and also serves as a motivation method to improve performance (Sung & Choi, 2014). The main purpose of training is to eliminate performance discrepancies whether current or anticipated so that the employees are equipped with relevant skills to perform their job tasks. Kiruja and Mukuru (2018) mentions that training is particularly important for purposes of improving performance both at individual or organizational level and especially in organizations that report a decline in performance levels. Training and development policies and programmes are essential components in the process of developing talent, ensuring that people acquire and enhance the skills and competencies they need which would translated into positive results. At the same time, training and development activities are important means of developing managers and gaining the engagement and commitment of talented staff by giving them opportunities to grow in their present roles and to progress to higher level roles. Trained employees perform well which may lead to their promotion. By matching the size and skills of the workforce to the productive requirements of the organization, and by raising the quality of individual employee' contributions to production, organizations there would be a significant improvement on employee performance (Kiruja & Mukuru, 2018). Successful organizations set training and development as a priority by assessing the employees training needs through measuring the acquired skill set versus job requirements. The organization then comes up with a training program considering the method that would be adopted either on-job or off-job, classroom setting or practical experiments in enhancing the knowledge and information employees possess.

Hafeez and Akbar (2015) mentions that the training scope and content is a measure of how successful a county would be and using valuable development programs including mentorship programs. The more experienced employees' coach, mentor and train new staffs in handling workplace activities. Putting in place all these elements increases the probability of having a successful training and development programs that improves the employee performance. In today's era of disruption and rapid technological advancement, the demands for organizational competence development are on the rise (Richter et al., 2020; Schaeffer, 2017). The acquisition of new competences and successful competency management of employees are crucial for the survival of organizations that face rapid transformation (Cascio & Montealegre, 2023; Kauffeld, 2024; Kraiger & Ford, 2021). Formal training is a central element in shaping employee competence acquisition and is increasingly recognized as essential (Bonekamp & Sure, 2020; Hilkenmeier et al., 2021; Kauffeld, 2024). As disruptive technologies continue to reshape the business landscape external expertise can play a critical role to foster innovation and stay competitive, providing new perspectives and insights into new processes and practices (Hilkenmeier et al., 2021).

In recent years, informal learning in organizations has been considered particularly crucial. However, the constantly changing work environment and the increasingly complex and dynamic workplace demand new competences acquired from formal training (Bhatti et al., 2019; Bonekamp & Sure, 2020; Richter et al., 2020). Formal learning was once regarded as chronically delayed, but in today's disruptive times, it has regained importance because new competencies have become increasingly complex and intricate, often surpassing the capacity of self-directed informal learning (Kauffeld &

Paulsen,2018). At the same time, the perspective of accompanying employees on their individual learning path and therefore combining formal and informal learning is gaining ground (Blume et al.,2023; Decius et al.,2023; Kauffeld,2024; Richter et al.,2020). Training refers to a planned effort by an institution or organization to facilitate the learning process of its leaders and employees so as to gain competences that would result in an improvement of their performance at an individual level and at overall organizational level (Blume et al.,2023). Training is a program that helps employees to learn the specific knowledge or skills to improve performance in their current roles. The training programs can be done in several ways, either as a planned and formal manner or informal and semi-structured, as long as information is passed from one party to another. Employee training is a planned and purposive activity aimed at enhancing the skills, knowledge and competencies necessary in improving employee performance (Pete 2025).

Tahir, Yousafzai, Jan and Hashim (2014) noted that employee training is beneficial in bridging the gap between what employees know and the information required in successful completing a work task. Many employees in organizations welcome the idea of training and development, as it serves to equip them with necessary skills to perform their duties. Training equips employees with necessary knowledge to handle their assigned work tasks, but development is futuristic, looking at the skill set needed to handle new work jobs and holding positions of authority within the organization. According to Hafeez and Akbar (2015) developing an individual involves equipping the person with conceptual and theoretical knowledge on work operations and processes. Valid training and development programs are responsive to the fast-paced market place and changing market needs and preferences. Employees must be regularly updated on changing customer preferences, industry regulation and policies, current workplace management and advanced organizational operations, for them to increase their productivity. Such knowledge would ensure that the employees do not only have technical work knowledge but are responsible and able to analyze and solve workplace problems, hence improving their performance (Sung & Choi, 2014).

Training should not be a one-time event, but organizations seeking continuous improvement in their performance, must invest in lifelong training. In showing commitment to improved performance, the management and leadership of organizations must set a sufficient budget for staff trainings. The budget and strategic plans must recognize that training and development impacts knowledge and skills to employees and used as a major source of improved performance and competitive advantage in the global market (Tahir, et al., 2014). Since training is a need-oriented effort, determining the level, type and duration of the training is the prime importance at this stage of the process. Consequently, assessing organizational training need shows the diagnostic phase of planning training aims. As cited on Khan and Masrek (2017); Priyadarshini and Dave(2013), training needs assessment is a strategic process that involves identifying the organization, industries goals, competency gathering, and analyzing the information, determining the gaps between the present situation and the future condition. The assessment phase includes employee and employer performance issues to know if training is needed. During the assessment, it is important to consider non-training factors such as compensations, organizational structure, job design, and physical work plans.

Mondy et al.,(2016) states that a systematic approach of training needs assessment activity focuses on the firm's strategic mission, goals and corporate plans are studied, along with the results of strategic human resource planning. A training needs assessment helps companies or organizations determine whether training is necessary. Similarly, Training needs assessment is the process of analyzing the difference between what is currently occurring within a job or jobs and what is required either now or in the future-based on the organization's operations and strategic goals (Lussier & Hendon,2020). There are three training needs analysis (organizational analyses, task /job analysis, person analysis (Armstrong 2014, Lussier & Hendon, 2020; Mathis & Jackson,2016; Mondy & Martocchio, 2016; Noe & Hollenbeck,2019), and (Hartoyo & Efendy,2017).

Performance is a measure of the achieved results against the set targets or plans. Performance is measured in financial terms as an indicator of returns on assets, investment, market size and profitability index or in non-financial terms like customer satisfaction, motivation to work, regularly going to work, teamwork and improved productivity per hour or day (Karatepe, 2013). Employee performance can be described as the record of outcomes achieved for each job function during a specific period time. It can be manifested in improvement in production, easiness in using the new technology, highly motivated workers. At the same time, employee performance can simply be seen as employees undertaking the activities as expected and outlined in their job description. The management and leadership of a county should assess employee performance on a basis of their expected undertakings either in annual, biannual or quarterly basis (Athar & Shah, 2015).

Employee performance is defined as the outcome or contribution of employees to make them attain goals while performance may be used to define what an organization has accomplished with respect to the process, results, relevance and success. Employee performance is everything about the performance of employees in a county or a company or an organization. It involves all aspects which directly or indirectly affect and relate to the work of the employees (Cascio & Montealegre, 2023). Employee performance is usually monitored through regular performance appraisals so as to ensure the achievement of specific tasks measured against predetermined or identified standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed (Gebrehiwot · 2023).

Every organization has a desire to see employee performance improve from one level to another in order to foster organizational performance and earn higher returns, expansion into new markets and higher profitability. High employee performance can be in terms of their level of cooperation and teamwork at the work place and at the same time, the ability of employees to achieve the set targets (Omolo, 2015). Employee performance is not concerned with the problem but rather looking for the solution to the problem for the gain of the individual and the whole organization. It further, looks at the employees' capacity and ability to accomplish the set goals in an effective and efficient way and using the available organizational resources.

County governments in Kenya continue to invest heavily on training of staff using various forms such as induction, benchmarking tours and workshops without corresponding mechanism of evaluating the effect of the skills acquired from the trainings on actual job performance of the employees. Review studies shows there exist a gap in existing literature on the specific skills from trainings that affect job performance even as numerous studies continue to report positive correlation between training and employee performance (Wachira et. al., 2021).

Employee performance is a critical factor in the effective service delivery of county governments. However, many county governments in Kenya face challenges related to inefficiencies, low productivity, and inadequate service provision, often attributed to gaps in employee skills and competencies. Training and development are widely recognized as essential strategies for enhancing employee performance, equipping staff with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies to improve service delivery. Despite the significant role of training and development, there is limited empirical evidence on how these initiatives impact employee performance in county governments. Many counties allocate substantial resources to training programs, yet the effectiveness of these programs remains unclear due to issues such as lack of proper needs assessment, poor implementation, and limited follow-up evaluation. Additionally, employees may not always apply the skills learned in training to their daily work, leading to minimal improvements in service delivery. This study sought to establish the effect of training needs assessment on performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru, Kenya

2. TRAINING NEEDS ASSESSMENT AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

Training is the process of upgrading the information and knowledge that recipients have on specific topics, events, operations and activities. Training is done to develop skills and pass over new operational knowledge, bringing about attitudinal and behavioral changes leading to improved capability of the trainees to handle their duties and work assignments effectively and efficiently (Kulkarni, 2013). Similarly, according to Obi-Anike and Ekwe (2014) while assessing the impact that training and development has on organizational effectiveness in the Nigerian public sector, revealing that training is seen as equipping employees with knowledge and skills to enable the group of trainees achieve the set strategic objectives and goals. Achievement of goals is made possible through the development of appropriate knowledge, skills and attitude of the employees.

As per the HRD policy and other HRM&D guidelines in the counties, planning for training shall be guided by the outcome of Training Needs Assessment and shall be designed in line with identified performance gaps linking training to closing of such gaps (Nderi et al. 2020). Training will be planned to upgrade core competencies, knowledge, skills and attitudes of public servants, with the aim of enhancing service delivery. Training Needs Assessment is an audit process or method of determining if a training need exists, and if it does, what training is required to fill the gap. TNA seeks to identify accurately the levels of the present situation, and the gap between the present status and desired status and may indicate problems that in turn can be translated into a training need (Nderi et al. 2020). The Human Resource Management and Development directorate will coordinate all the TNA activities at Departmental levels

The appropriate training can convert any employee into an effective manager through passing on information that can equip them with the competency to manage all organizational activities. In an effort to improve the performance of the entire

organization as well as individual performance, organizations must assess the job requirements versus the skills and knowledge of employees. Bridging the gap between the job requirement and inherent skills and knowledge is possible through training programs that respond to the needs.

Hafeez and Akbar (2015) while focusing on employee training and their performance with the case of pharmaceutical companies in Pakistan, noted that training of employees according to the knowledge gap exhibited in organization results in increasing their productivity through better job performance, efficient use of human resources and available resources, meeting the set goals and objectives, reduced cost due to less labor turnover, reduced errors, reduced accidents and absenteeism, more capable, and mobile work force and retention of the existing staff. The study further revealed that since employees are a major asset to the organization, the management of the pharmaceutical companies must understand the importance of spending income on training them so as to create competitiveness. Trained employees showcase the value in terms of demonstrating team work, communication skill, customer service, interpersonal relationship and reduced absenteeism while the development areas include job-satisfaction, employee motivation, new technologies, and efficiencies in process and innovation in strategies as its levers.

Sultana (2013) stated that it is evident that the more employees get relevant training, the efficient they become in their productivity and performance. In a study conducted by Meyer, Srinivas, Lal and Topolnysky (2017) on employee commitment and support for an organizational change, 60% of the sampled employees admitted that, impact of training on their work performance was excellent. They indicated also that, training content was relevant to achieving their personal needs, goals and self-development. It further indicated that a large number (60%) of the sampled employees admitted that impact of training on their work performance was excellent. The study also revealed the training content was relevant to achieving their personal needs, goals and self-development. Guest (1987) argues that policies are necessary to ensure that employee performance is evaluated, which in turn ensures that the appropriate training and development take place.

With the help of the performance appraisal reports and findings, the organization can be able to identify development needs. However, individuals themselves can help to indicate the areas requiring improvement as a result of the issues raised in the performance appraisal process and their career path needs. In an investigative study on training and development impact on performance of employees, Kum, Cowden and Karodia (2014) revealing that the management in organizations should approve training programs and content to ensure that the employees learn new formats of working. Onyango and Wanyoike (2014) on the effects of training on employee performance, showed that health workers in Siaya County exhibited low job satisfaction and 15 motivation which greatly affected their performance. The county set to change this trend by using training programs and their support was seen through funding the training programs while recommending the training to all health workers. This decision was reached due to the notion that training had a positive impact on the employee performance and their productivity levels. In essence, training is only effective in influencing employee performance when the fundamental aspects of process classification, assessing trainee needs, selecting an appropriate training methods and delivery modes. According to Asfaw, Argaw and Bayissa, (2015) on the training and development impact on the effectiveness of employee performance, sharing that training is effective only when the top leadership and organizational management give the project its support in terms of budgetary allocation, creating time for trainees to be taught either on the job or off-the-job and give it a go-ahead nod.

Employee performance is achieving and accomplishing specific and well-determined tasks in the organization, these tasks will be measured with well-planned and predefined goals, objectives (Safitri & Lathifah,2019). Armstrong(2020), stated that employee performance management is the continuous process of improving performance by setting individual and team goals that are aligned to the strategic goals of the organization, planning performance to achieve the goals, reviewing and assessing progress, and developing the knowledge, skills, and abilities of people (Armstrong,2020). Some of the main performance measurements are productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, quality and profitability (Aidan,2013; Armstrong,2020). Employee performance demonstrated the improvement in production by perfect use of new technology with the help of highly aggravated employees (Al-Omari et al., Citation2020). Manger used to set high standards for individual in order to measure the performance of employees for the betterment of organization (Buchanan. & Badham, 2020).

According to Landa (2018), training has a significant positive relationship with employee performance. Training is considered as a fundamental tool in the organizational capacity building to improve its performance and achieving its goals (Sasidaran, 2018). As cited in Afroz (2018), training and development is the organization's strategic instrument to improve

employee performance by acquiring and equipping employees with the cutting-edge skills and knowledge along with the right organization attitude by the best practice to do their tasks within the planned goals and objectives. Training is the main pillar that is significantly predicting employees' performance, it enhances their capabilities, capacities, competencies, and their recognition for their works and duties (Kenny & Nnamdi, 2019).

Some studies indicate that training and the employee's performance are inter-connected with several variables. For instance, Luo et al. (2021) investigated the relationship among training, supervisory mentoring, job satisfaction, and task performance, with the consideration of interpersonal helping's moderating role. The results show that training and supervisory mentoring have significant effects on job satisfaction and task performance; job satisfaction has a positive effect on task performance and along with supervisory mentoring, interpersonal helping has a moderating effect on task performance. As stated by Melian Gonzalez and Bulchand Gidumal (2018) on the investigation of the relationship among front office employee performance, information technologies (IT), service encounter, and critical incidents, IT takes part heavily in the task performance of front office workers, who rely on IT to get their job done. On the other hand, in service encounters, the value of the human presence is still high, and in most critical incidents IT do not participate. Sendawula et al. (2018) in the investigation of training and employee engagement on employee performance using evidence from Uganda's health sector considered the relationship among training, employee engagement, and employee performance. Therefore, training and the employee's performance are inter-connected with several variables.

3. METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive research design. This study was conducted in Nakuru County. The target population of this study were staff from the Nakuru county administration and specifically Middle Management System. Since the study population was small, the study worked with entire population which is census. Data collection instrument was questionnaire and other information relevant to the study. A structured questionnaire was administered to the respondents. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. Once data is collected, it was crosschecked and verified for errors, completeness and consistency. It was then be coded, entered and analyzed descriptively using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 23). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables in the study hypotheses. ANOVA multiple linear regression analysis was adopted computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variable and the dependent.

4. DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Effect of training needs assessment on performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru, Kenya.

The first specific objective of the study was to establish the effect of training needs assessment on performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru. The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on statements relating to the effect of training needs assessment on performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru, Kenya. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in Table 4.1.

From the results, the respondents agreed that as per the HRD policy and other HRM&D guidelines in the counties, planning for training shall be guided by the outcome of Training Needs Assessment and shall be designed in line with identified performance gaps linking training to closing of such gaps. This is supported by a mean of 2.201 (std. dv = 0.633). In addition, as shown by a mean of 1.702 (std. dv = 0.791), the respondents agreed that TNA seeks to identify accurately the levels of the present situation, and the gap between the present status and desired status and may indicate problems that in turn can be translated into a training need. Further, the respondents agreed that the appropriate training can convert any employee into an effective manager through passing on information that can equip them with the competency to manage all organizational activities. This is shown by a mean of 2.981 (std. dv = 0.653). The respondents also agreed that training needs assessment enhances employee performance. This is shown by a mean of 2.013 (std. dv = 0.601).

With a mean of 3.225 (std. dv = 0.713), the respondents agreed that all employees in the county government requires to be assessed for appropriate training.

The respondents also agreed that all employees in the county government requires to be assessed for appropriate training. This is shown by a mean of 2.981 (std. dv = 0.879). The respondents also agreed that Training needs assessment play a very important role in managing the employees in an organisation. This is shown by a mean of 3.399 (std. dv = 0.678).

Table 4.1: Effect of training needs assessment on performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru, Kenya;

	Mean	Std. Deviation
As per the HRD policy and other HRM&D guidelines in the counties, planning for training shall be guided by the outcome of Training Needs Assessment and shall be designed in line with identified performance gaps linking training to closing of such gaps.	2.201	0.633
TNA seeks to identify accurately the levels of the present situation, and the gap between the present status and desired status and may indicate problems that in turn can be translated into a training need	1.702	0.791
The appropriate training can convert any employee into an effective manager through passing on information that can equip them with the competency to manage all organizational activities.	2.981	0.653
Training needs assessment enhances employee performance	3.225	0.713
All employees in the county government requires to be assessed for appropriate training.	2.912	0.879
Training needs assessment play a very important role in managing the employees in an organisation	3.399	0.678
Aggregate	2.737	0.724

4.1.1. Effect of performance of County government of Nakuru.

The objective was to assess the effect of on performance of County government of Nakuru in Kenya. The reliability for performance of County government of Nakuru in Kenya. The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on various statements relating to the effect of on performance of County government of Nakuru in Kenya. The reliability for performance of County government of Nakuru. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in table 4.2.

From the results, the respondents agreed that employee performance is achieving and accomplishing specific and well-determined tasks in the organization, these tasks will be measured with well-planned and predefined goals, objectives. This is supported by a mean of 3.124 (std. dv = 0.879). In addition, as shown by a mean of 2.917 (std. dv = 0.623), the respondents agreed that Employee performance management is the continuous process of improving performance by setting individual and team goals that are aligned to the strategic goals of the organization, planning performance to achieve the goals, reviewing and assessing progress, and developing the knowledge, skills, and abilities of people. The respondents further agreed that the main performance measurements are productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, quality and profitability. This is shown by a mean of 2.251 (std. dv = 0.785). The respondents also agreed that Training is considered as a fundamental tool in the organizational capacity building to improve its performance and achieving its goals. This is shown by a mean of 2.111 (std. dv = 0.622). With a mean of 2.764 (std. dv = 0.646), the respondents agreed that Training is the main pillar that is significantly predicting employees' performance, it enhances their capabilities, capacities, competencies, and their recognition for their works and duties. The respondent also agreed that Training method, content etc are very vital in enhancing organisation performance. This is shown by a mean of 2.482 (std. dv = 0.731).

Table 4.2: Performance of County Government of Nakuru in Kenya.

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Employee performance is achieving and accomplishing specific and well-determined tasks in the organization, these tasks will be measured with well-planned and predefined goals, objectives	3.124	0.879
Employee performance management is the continuous process of improving performance by setting individual and team goals that are aligned to the strategic goals of the organization, planning performance to achieve the goals, reviewing and assessing progress, and developing the knowledge, skills, and abilities of people	2.917	0.623

The main performance measurements are productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, quality and profitability	2.251	0.785
Training is considered as a fundamental tool in the organizational capacity building to improve its performance and achieving its goals.	2.111	0.622
Training is the main pillar that is significantly predicting employees' performance, it enhances their capabilities, capacities, competencies, and their recognition for their works and duties	2.764	0.646
Training method, content etc are very vital in enhancing organisation performance	2.482	0.731
Aggregate	2.606	0.714

4.2 Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics in the current study focused on correlation and regression analysis. Correlation analysis was used to determine the strength of the relationship while regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between dependent variable (performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru Kenya) and the independent variable (training needs assessment).

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

The present study used Pearson correlation analysis to determine the strength of association between independent variables (training needs assessment) and the dependent variable (performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru) dependent variable. Pearson correlation coefficient range between zero and one, where by the strength of association increase with increase in the value of the correlation coefficients. The current study employed Taylor (2018) correlation coefficient ratings where by 0.80 to 1.00 depicts a very strong relationship, 0.60 to 0.79 depicts strong, 0.40 to 0.59 depicts moderate, 0.20 to 0.39 depicts weak.

Table 4.3: Correlation Coefficients

		Employee Performance	Training needs assessment
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	80	
Training needs assessment	Pearson Correlation	.563**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	80	80

From the results, there was a very strong relationship between training needs assessment and performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya. ($r = .563$, p value = 0.002). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.002 was less than 0.05 (significant level).

4.2.2 Regression Analysis

Multivariate regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between independent variables (training needs assessment) and the dependent variable (performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya).

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.659	.634	.626	.559239

a. Predictors: (Constant), training needs assessment.

The model summary was used to explain the variation in the dependent variable that could be explained by the independent variables. The r-squared for the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable was 0.634. This implied that 63.4% of the variation in the dependent variable (performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya) could be explained by independent variables (training needs assessment).

Table 4.5: Analysis of Variance

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	60.226	1	51.292	80.441	.001 ^b
1 Residual	17.621	79	.060		
Total	77.847	80			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya

b. Predictors: (Constant), training needs assessment

The ANOVA was used to determine whether the model was a good fit for the data. F calculated was 80.441 and p value was 0.000 the model was considered as a good fit for the data. Therefore, the model can be used to predict the effect of training needs assessment on performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya.

Table 4.6: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.524	.121		4.125	.000
	Training needs analysis	.712	.306	1.701	3.517	.000

a Dependent Variable: Performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya

Table 4.6 showed that if training needs assessment, training methods, training content and development programs are all held constant, performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya would be at 0.524.

Performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya = 0.524 + 0.712 (training needs assessment).

The regression model was as follows:

$$Y = 0.524 + 0.712X_1 + \varepsilon$$

According to the results, training needs assessment has a significant effect on performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya. $\beta_1=0.712$, p value= 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study concluded that training needs assessment has a significant effect on performance of employees at County governments of Nakuru in Kenya. $\beta_1=0.712$, p value= 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05. The study came up with the following recommendations; the management should come up with HRD policy and other HRM&D guidelines in the counties, planning for training shall be guided by the outcome of Training Needs Assessment and shall be designed in line with identified performance gaps linking training to closing of such gaps

The development programs can be achieved using coaching and mentorship programs which aims at passing the information to other employees and that Mentoring improves employee job satisfaction and increases their work output leading to higher chances of retaining such employees.

REFERENCES

- [1] Amadi, E. J. (2014). The effect of training and development on Employees' performance; at Safaricom limited Call centre. *Unpublished (MBA) project*, University of Nairobi.
- [2] Athar, R., & Shah, F. M. (2015). Impact of Training on Employee Performance (Banking Sector Karachi). *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSRJBM)* e-ISSN, 2278.
- [3] Awais Bhatti, M., Mohamed Battour, M., Pandiyani Kaliani Sundram, V., & Aini Othman, A. (2013). Transfer of training: does it truly happen? An examination of support, instrumentality, retention and learner readiness on the transfer motivation and transfer of training. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 37(3), 273-297.

- [4] Bhat, Z. H. (2013). Impact of training on employee performance: A Study of retail banking sector in India. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 3(6), 292-293.
- [5] Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications.
- [6] Falola, H. O., Osibanjo, A. O., & Ojo, S. I. (2014). Effectiveness of Training and Development on Employees' performance and Organisation Competitiveness in the Nigerian Banking Industry. *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov. Economic Sciences. Series V*, 7(1), 161.
- [7] F. Baldi, L. Trigeorgis(2020). Valuing human capital career development: a real options approach. *J. Intellect. Cap.*, 21 (5) (2020), pp. 781-807, 10.1108/JIC-062019-0134
- [8] Gagliardi, A. R., Webster, F., Perrier, L., Bell, M., & Straus, S. (2014). Exploring mentorship as a strategy to build capacity for knowledge translation research and practice: *a scoping systematic review. Implementation Science*, 9(1), 122.
- [9] Githinji, A. (2014). Effects of training on employee performance: a case study of United Nations Support Office for the African Union Mission in Somalia (*Doctoral dissertation, United States International University-Africa*).
- [10] Hafeez, U., & Akbar, W. (2015). "Impact of Training on Employees Performance" (Evidence from Pharmaceutical Companies in Karachi, Pakistan). *Business Management and Strategy*, 6(1), 49-64. Hassan, S. (2016). Impact of HRM Practices on Employee's Performance. *Int J Acad Res Account, Financ Manag Sci*, 6, 15-22.
- [11] Kiruja, E. K., & Mukuru, E. (2018). Effect of motivation on employee performance in public middle level Technical Training Institutions in Kenya. *IJAME*.
- [12] Kulkarni, P. P. (2013). A literature review on training & development and quality of work life. *Researchers World*, 4(2), 136.
- [13] Kum, F. D., Cowden, R., & Karodia, A. M. (2014). The impact of training and development on employee performance: A case study of ESCON 54 Consulting. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics and Management Studies*, 3(3), 72-105.
- [14] Lancaster, S., Di Milia, L., & Cameron, R. (2013). Supervisor behaviours that facilitate training transfer. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 25(1), 6-22.
- [15] Larsen, H. H. (2017). Key issues in training and development. In *Policy and practice in European human resource management* (pp. 107-121). *Routledge*.
- [16] Lewis, S. (2015). Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches. *Health promotion practice*, 16(4), 473-475.
- [17] Mburu, D. K. (2017). Influence of transformational leadership role on performance of virtual project teams in Safaricom Limited.
- [18] Mertler, C. A. (2018). *Introduction to educational research*. Sage Publications.
- [19] Neuman, W. L. (2013). *Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches*. *Pearson education*.
- [20] Obi-Anike, H. O., & Ekwe, M. C. (2014). Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Effectiveness: Evidence from Selected Public Sector Organizations in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(29), 66-75.
- [21] Odhong, A. E., Were, S., & Omolo, J. (2014). Effect of human capital management drivers on organizational performance in Kenya. A case of investment and mortgages bank ltd. *European Journal of Business Management*, 2(1), 341- 356.
- [22] Onyango, J. W., & Wanyoike, D. M. (2014). Effects of training on employee performance: a survey of health workers in Siaya County, Kenya. *European Journal of Material Sciences*, 1(1), 11-15.

- [23] Pete Ford (2025). The Impact of Corporate Training on Business Growth in 2025
- [24] Rusinovci, X. (2015). The Effects of Persistent Training and Development on Personnel Performance and Productivity. *International Journal*, 4(4).
- [25] Tahir, N., Yousafzai, I. K., Jan, S., & Hashim, M. (2014). The Impact of Training and Development on Employees Performance and Productivity. A case study of United Bank Limited Peshawar City, KPK, Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(4), 86.
- [26] Valentine, K. (2017). Effect of Training and Development on Employee Performance at Kakamega County General Hospital, Kenya.
- [27] Wenzel, R. (2014). Training-related Motivation and Transfer Outcomes: The Role of Proactive Transfer Behaviour and Positive Psychological States (*Doctoral dissertation, University of Western Australia*).
- [28] Yin, R. K. (2013). Validity and generalization in future case study evaluations. *Evaluation*, 19(3), 321-332.
- [29] Yin, R. K. (2017). *Case study research and applications: Design and methods*. Sage publications.